

Three new *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 species (Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae) from Papua New Guinea and Fiji

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Key words: Coleoptera, Mycetophagidae, *Litargus*, taxonomy, new species, Fiji, Papua New Guinea.

Abstract. *Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus* sp. nov. from Papua New Guinea, *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* sp. nov. and *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* sp. nov. both from Fiji Islands are described, illustrated and compared with a similar species, *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879.

Introduction

The genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 can be divided into the following two subgenera: *Litargosomus* Motschulsky, 1858 and *Litargus* s. str. and currently contains 95 species worldwide (Háva 2022, 2025). From Papua New Guinea only one species, *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879 is known; from the Fiji Islands only one species, *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879 is known. Evenhuis & Ramsdale (2006, last revised in 2013) mentioned the species without detailed data.

The new species described here are from Fiji: Viti Levu and from Papua New Guinea: West New Britain Province.

Material and method

The type material is deposited in the following collections:

BMNH - British Museum Natural History London, England (D. Telnov);

JHAC - Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic.

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in

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species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of head to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

Results

Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus sp. nov.

Figs 1-4

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 1.8 mm, EW 0.9 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; black, covered with brown and yellow recumbent setation; elytra brown with yellowish patterns (Figs 1-3).

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by yellow, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres light brown, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 4); palpomeres light brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown with large dark brown spot, covered by light brown recumbent setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, yellow, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum brown, triangular, with short recumbent light brown setation.

Elytra brown with yellowish patterns covered by yellow recumbent setation, brown patterns covered by brown setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex (Figs 1-3). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta - mesoventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs entirely light brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

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Abdominal visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium light brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very similar to *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879, but differs from it by the black elytral cuticula, arrangement of yellowish elytral patterns and structure of antennae.

Type material. Holotype (♀) labelled: PAPUA N. GUINEA, W. New Britain Prov., Dani Oilpalm Res. Stn., 28.viii.1982, RNB. Prior. 1984.252 / No. 35669 on Oilpalm, C.I.E. A16759 / Pres by Comm Inst. Ent. B.M. 1985-1 / *Litargus* sp. det. R.B. Madge 1985, (BMNH). Paratypes (3 ♀♀): the same data s holotype, (2 BMNH, 1 JHAC); (1 ♀): PAPUA N. GUINEA, W. New Britain Prov., Dani Oilpalm Res. Stn. Hoskins / 1-3.xi.1980, on Oliplams K1662, C.I.E. A12863 / Pres by Comm Inst. Ent. B.M. 1985-1 / *Litargus* sp. det. R.B. Madge 1981, (specimen without abdomen), (BMNH).

Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed labels with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE (or PARATYPE) *Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Etymology. Tomonymic, named for the Papua New Guinea, where the holotype was collected.

Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae sp. nov.

Figs 8-11

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 2.3 mm, EW 1.2 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; black, covered with brown and yellow recumbent setation; elytra black with yellowish spots (Fig. 8).

Head black, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by brown, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres brown, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 10); palpomeres dark brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

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Pronotum brown, covered by brown recumbent setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts. Scutellum brown, triangular, with short recumbent brown setation.

Elytra brown with yellowish isolated spots covered by light brown recumbent setation forming longitudinal striation, brown patterns covered by brown setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex, apical part without tip (Figs 8-9). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta - mesoventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 11).

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is similar to *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879, but differs from it by the arrangement of yellowish elytral patterns and structure of antennae; from *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* **sp. nov.** differs by elytral setation (setation forming longitudinal striae), apex of elytron (Fig. 9), structure of antennae (Fig. 10) and male genitalia, parameres broad (Fig. 11).

Type material. Holotype (♂) labelled: Fiji, Viti Levu, Suva env., Colo I Suva, 18.05753S 178.46407E, 7.12.2024, L. Bureš Weyrová lgt., (JHAC).

Specimens of the presently described species are provided with red, printed labels with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Etymology. Patronymic, dedicated to my friends and collectors of the new species, Lukáš Bureš and Dominika Weyrová (Brno, Czech Republic).

Figs 1-4. *Litargus (Litargosomus) papuanus* sp. nov.: 1. habitus, dorsal aspect of holotype; 2. habitus, dorso-lateral aspect of holotype; 3. habitus, dorsal aspect of paratype; 4. antenna;

Figs 5-7. *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879: 5. habitus, dorsal aspect; 6. antenna; 7. male genitalia.

Figs 8-11. *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* sp. nov.: 8. habitus, dorsal aspect of holotype; 9. elytral apex; 10. antenna; 11. male genitalia.

Figs 12-15. *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* sp. nov.: 12. habitus, dorsal aspect of holotype; 13. elytral apex; 14. antenna; 15. male genitalia.

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Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis sp. nov.

Figs. 12-15

Description. Male. Body measurements TL 2.2 mm, EW 1.0 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; black, covered with brown and yellow recumbent setation; elytra black with yellowish spots (Fig. 12).

Head black, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by brown, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres brown, antennal club with three antennomeres (Fig. 14); palpomeres dark brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, covered by brown recumbent setation, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures; widest posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; lateral sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum brown, triangular, with short recumbent brown setation.

Elytra brown with yellowish isolated spots covered by light brown recumbent setation not forming striation, brown patterns covered by brown setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex, apical part without tip (Figs 12-13). Epipleuron brown, covered with brown recumbent setation.

Meta - mesoventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation, finely punctate.

Legs brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, finely punctate, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 15).

Female. Unknown.

Type material. Holotype (♂) labelled: Fiji Is., Viti Levu, Navai, vii.2016, exEbay, (JHAC).

Specimens of the presently described species are provided

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with red, printed labels with text as follows: „HOLOTYPE *Litargus (Litargosomus) fijiensis* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is similar to *Litargus (Litargosomus) vestitus* Sharp, 1879, but differs from it by the arrangement of yellowish elytral patterns and structure of antennae; from *Litargus (Litargosomus) buresweyrovae* **sp. nov.** differs by elytral setation (setation not forming longitudinal striae), apex of elytron (Fig. 13), structure of antennae (Fig. 14) and male genitalia, parameres more narrow (Fig. 15).

Etymology. Tomonymic, named for the Fiji Islands, where the holotype was collected.

Acknowledgments. I am obliged very much to Dmitry Telnov (BMNH) for loaning me the interesting material, to Lukáš Bureš (Brno, Czech Republic) for donated me the interesting material and to Larry G. Bezark (California, U.S.A.) for comments and English revision of the manuscript.

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Received: 20.12.2025

Accepted: 12.03.2026